

Phoenix, AZ, 1999 meeting

IMIA WG6 meeting 'Terminology and natural language in medicine' Presentations & papers of IMIA-WG6, Medical Concept and Language Representation

- Change Management of Shared and Local Health-Care Terminologies. Yuval Shahar, D. E. Oliver
- Customizable and Ontology-Enhanced Medical Information Retrieval Interfaces. Gony L, Tolle KM, Chen H.
- Terminology Tools: State of the Art and Practical Lessons Cimino, JJ
- Ontological Issues in using a Description Logic to Represent Medical Concepts - Experience from GALEN. Rector, A Rogers, J
- Developing natural language understanding applications for healthcare: a case study on interpreting drug therapy information from discharge summaries. Ceusters W, Jan Lorré, Annelies Harnie, Bert Van Den Bossche.
- Semantic Augmentation of Description Logic based Terminologies Elkin PL, Harris M, Ogren PV, Buntrock ID, Brown SH, Solbrig HR, Chute CG